

In vitro biocompatibility and mucoadhesion of montmorillonite chitosan nanocomposite: A new drug delivery

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Abstract

A "Clay Bio Polymer Nanocomposite" (CBPN) to be used in drug release was prepared by dispersion of montmorillonite (Mt) particles in chitosan (Ch) solution. The obtained hybrid material was characterized for in vitro biocompatibility on Caco-2 cell cultures. Cytotoxicity and cell proliferation of the nanocomposite were tested, comparing results with free Ch and Mt. Cell proliferation was assessed both by WST-1 test and wound-healing measurements by means of Image Analysis Software. The last method is a proof of concept test that has the advantage of direct visualization and quantification of cell growth. Nanocomposite was also characterized for hydration (water uptake) pattern and mucoadhesive properties, which were considered as important features for the application of this material in modified release systems. Results showed that the prepared CBPN showed good biocompatibility in the range 5–500 µg/ml, being also able to effectively stimulate cell proliferation. Moreover, nanocomposite possessed mucoadhesive properties combined with low solubility in acidic environment. We conclude that interaction between Ch and Mt produced a new biohybrid material that can be considered as promising candidate for modified drug delivery formulations.

1. Introduction

In the last decade, there has been growing interest in the development of nanocomposites between clay minerals and biopolymers for pharmaceutical applications (Viseras et al., 2008, 2010). These hybrid materials can combine the properties of both components (inorganic and organic), such as swelling, water uptake, mechanical characteristics, thermal behavior, rheology and bioadhesion (Pongjanyakul et al., 2005; Wu and Wu, 2006; Günster et al., 2007; Khunawattanakul et al., 2008; Pongjanyakul and Suksri, 2009, 2010). They could be formed from a variety of biopolymers and clay minerals. Among them, Mt/ch nanocomposites are receiving greater attention, especially for biomedical (tissue engineering) (Katti et al., 2008; Haroun et al., 2009; Verma et al., 2010) and biopharmaceutical (modified release) (Wang et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2009; Khunawattanakul et al., 2010; Nanda et al., 2011) applications.

Ch is a cationic copolymer formed by N-acetylglucosamine and D-glucosamine units, being obtained by the natural occurring polysaccharide chitin (Fig. 1). It is widely used in pharmaceutical field, because of its suitable characteristics, including chemical safety, biodegradability, biocompatibility, antibacterial activity and mucoadhesive properties (Illum, 1998).

Mt is a layered hydrated aluminum silicate whose unit cell is composed of one Al-octahedral sheet (O) sandwiched between two Si-tetrahedral sheets (T). It possesses a net negative charge due to isomorphous ionic substitutions in the T-O-T structure. This charge is compensated by interlayer hydrated cations, which can be exchanged by a variety of organic molecules (Bergaya et al., 2006; Aguzzi et al., 2007). In particular, ch chains have been described to intercalate with Na⁺-Mt, because of their hydrophilic and cationic character, giving hybrid nanocomposite materials with interesting properties (Darder et al., 2003). Other works showed that the concentration of the clay mineral is a critical parameter in Mt/ch nanocomposites to achieve materials with enhanced properties (mechanical, thermal and/or electro-stimuli response) in comparison with the pure components (Wang et al., 2005; Xu et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2007). For example, nanocomposite hydrogels containing 2% (wt/wt) of Mt showed improved release behavior of vitamin B₁₂, compared with that of the pure Ch (Liu et al., 2008). Ratio between Mt and Ch was a crucial factor also in the case of nanocomposites prepared to control release of the chemotherapeutic agent doxorubicin (Yuan et al., 2010). pH-dependent release profiles were found for these nanocomposites, which were described as promising supports for colonic prolonged drug delivery.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of chitin (left) and Ch (right).

The majority of the studies are devoted to the physicochemical and biopharmaceutical characterisation of Mt/ch nanocomposites; however, their biocompatibility for drug release has been evaluated only by Depan et al. (2009).

In a previous work, a nanocomposite between Ch and Mt was prepared by simple solid-liquid interaction; the effective polymer/clay mineral complexation was confirmed by thermal analysis and slower drug release was observed in comparison with Ch and Mt alone (Aguzzi et al., 2010). In vitro biocompatibility was followed by cytotoxicity and cell proliferation in this paper, for further characterization. The effects of the nanocomposite were screened on Caco-2 cell cultures as a representative type of intestinal cells considering an oral administration and delivery. Cell proliferation was assayed by two different techniques: WST-1 test and wound-healing measurements. The last method has the advantage that allows a direct visualization of cell growth. Nanocomposites were also characterized for hydration (water uptake) pattern and mucoadhesive properties, which were considered as important features for the application of these materials in modified release systems.

2. Materials and methods

The polymer used was Ch base with low viscosity* (12 mPa*s) and deacetylation degree of 98% (Giusto Faravelli, Italy) (*Viscosity measurements were performed on 1% (w/v) solutions in HCl 0.1M at 90 1/s with rotational rheometer equipped with coaxial cylinders C14 (Bohlin CS, Bohlin Instrument Division, Metrics Group Ltd., Cirencester, UK). Ch acetate was used as control in cell experiments. It was obtained by dissolving Ch base in aqueous acetic acid (1% vol/vol) and freeze drying (Edwards mod RV8) the polymer obtained solution.

The clay mineral was a marketed pharmaceutical-grade Mt (Veegum HS[®]), kindly gifted by Vanderbilt Company S.A. (USA).

Ch and Mt powders were pulverized in a ball miller (IG.W2/E, Giuliani, Italy) and then sieved to separate a rigorous size fraction (45–75 μm) to limit variability of the data. The selected fraction was kept in a desiccator until required.

2.1. Preparation of chitosan/clay mineral nanocomposite

Mt/ch nanocomposite was prepared following Aguzzi et al. (2010). Briefly, Ch was dissolved in aqueous acetic acid (1% vol/vol) at the concentration of 1% (wt/vol). Then, Mt was added to the polymer solution in the wt:wt ratio (2:1 Ch:Mt) corresponding to their maximum binding capacity, as calculated by interaction isotherms. Dispersion was stirred by a magnetic bar for 48 h at room temperature, washed with distilled water and then freeze dried. The product obtained was milled and sieved to select the size fraction between 45 and 75 μm .

2.2. Water uptake measurements

Water uptake experiments were carried out using a modified Enslin apparatus (Ferrari et al., 1991). Measurements were performed on 20 mg of nanocomposite, in acidic medium (0.1 M HCl) for 2000 s. For comparison, measurements were also performed on pure Ch and clay mineral powders, at the same granulometric fraction as the nanocomposite. Powders were laid on dialysis membrane discs (cut off 14,000 Da), which were placed on the sample holder of the apparatus

to retain dissolved Ch molecules and avoid sample mass lost. Membranes alone were used for blank measurements. Six replicates were performed on each sample.

2.3. Mucoadhesion measurements

Mucoadhesive properties were investigated by TA-XT2 Plus Texture Analyser (Stable Micro Systems, Enco, Italy) using porcine gastric mucin (Type II) (Sigma, Italy) as biological substrate. 40 mg of samples were hydrated in pH 5.0 phosphate buffer (European Pharmacopeia (EP) 6.0) and then laid on a filter paper fixed with double sided adhesive tape on the bottom of the upper probe of the apparatus. 30 μl of an 8% (wt/wt) mucin dispersion in phosphate buffer pH 7 (EP 6.0) were applied on a filter paper disc (diameter=10 mm), fixed in the lower probe of the apparatus and faced to the sample. The upper probe with the sample was lowered at a speed of 1.0 mms^{-1} onto the surface of the lower probe and a downward force (preload) of 2500 mN was applied for 1 min to ensure intimate contact between the sample and the mucin dispersion and to allow the formation of the mucoadhesive joints. After a 1 min rest, the upper probe was moved upwards at a constant speed of 4.0 mms^{-1} until the complete separation of the two surfaces occurred. The detachment force (mN) and the adhesive work (calculated from the area under the force-distance curve, AUC ($\text{mN}\cdot\text{s}$)) were recorded and simultaneously collected on a personal computer (Texture Exponent Software 32, Stable Microsystem, Enco, Italy). Blank measurements were performed using phosphate buffer pH 7 instead of the mucin suspension.

The normalized mucoadhesion parameter ($\Delta\text{AUC}/\text{AUC}$) was calculated according to the following equation (Ferrari et al., 1997):

$$\Delta\text{AUC}/\text{AUC} = (\text{AUC}_m - \text{AUC}_{\text{blank}}) / \text{AUC}_{\text{blank}}$$

where AUC_m is the work of adhesion obtained in presence of mucin and $\text{AUC}_{\text{blank}}$ is the work of adhesion obtained by the blank. Such normalization allowed comparing the mucoadhesive properties of samples characterised by different cohesive properties (viscosity) (Ferrari et al., 1997). Eight replicates were performed on each sample.

2.4. Cell cultures

Human colorectal adenocarcinoma cell lines (Caco-2) were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, USA). Cells were grown at 37 °C, 5% CO₂ atmosphere (PBIinternational, Italy) in pH 7.4 Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) (Lonza, Italy) containing 20% vol/vol heat inactivated Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Euroclone, Italy), penicillin (100 IU/ml), streptomycin (0.1 mg/ml) and 1% vol/vol non essential aminoacids (Sigma Aldrich, Italy). The culture medium was changed twice weekly during maintenance.

2.4.1. Cell viability measurements

Cell viability was estimated by the (4-(3-(4-Iodophenyl)-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-2H-5-tetrazolio)-1,3-benzene disulfonate) (WST-1) assay (Roche Diagnostics GmbH, Roche Molecular Biochemicals, Bioidea, Italy). This reagent is metabolically reduced mainly by mitochondria in viable cells to a water soluble formazan product, allowing direct absorbance measures after experiments (Ishiyama et al., 1996).

Confluent Caco-2 cells (70–90% confluence) were plated with the above described medium in 96-well plates (growth area 0,36 cm², Greiner Bio-one, PBI International, Italy) at a density of 1 × 10⁵ cells/cm² and cultured for 24 h (37 °C, 5% CO₂). Then, the medium was removed and 200 µl of nanocomposite dispersions at three different concentrations (5, 50, 500 µg/ml in medium without serum) were added to each well. For comparison, experiments were also done on Ch and clay mineral alone, at the same concentrations as the nanocomposites (Table 1). Complete medium and Triton®X100 (Fluka, Italy) were used as positive and negative controls, respectively. The plates were then incubated (37 °C, 5% CO₂) for different times, before being subjected to the WST-1 assay. The incubation time was 3 h for cytotoxicity and 24 h for cell proliferation assays. Subsequently, the medium was replaced by 100 µl of WST-1 10% v/v in HBSS (“Hanks’ balanced salt solution”) pH 7.4 and incubated for 3 h. At the end of the tests, the absorbance was assayed by using ELISA plate reader (iMark™ Microplate Absorbance Reader mod. 550, BioRad, Italy) equipped with mechanical plate shaker at 450 nm wavelength with a wavelength of 650 nm. The data were expressed as the mean percentage of viable cells as compared to the respective control (untreated cultures).

2.4.2. Wound-healing measurements

Wound-healing measurements were performed to directly evaluate cell proliferation. Experiments were carried out using a µ-Dish (Ibidi, Giardini, Italy) with an insert which delineates two distinct growth areas (growth area 2 × 0.22 cm²) (Fig. 2). Caco-2 cells were seeded at 10⁵ cells/cm² in each chamber (seeding volume of 70 µl) grown to confluence. After removal of the insert a cell free gap (“wound”) (500 µm ± 50 µm) remained. Cells were put in contact with 500 µl of medium without serum containing nanocomposite (50 µg/ml), with corresponding concentrations of free Ch and clay mineral. Dishes were reincubated over a total period of 72 h. The growth of cells over each sample was investigated by taking photographs after fixed times (24, 48 and 72 h) using an inverted microscope (PBI International, Italy) at a magnification of 250 × and the size of the gap between the chambers was taken as a measure of cell proliferation as a function of time. The digitalized images were elaborated by a suitable software (UTHSCSA Image Tool version 3.00, The University of Texas Health Science Center, USA), that allowed to measure the area left by the cell growth at each time. The % of wound areas at different times were calculated considering 100 the mean area measured for each sample at time zero. At least three different pictures were analyzed for each sample and each time.

2.4.3. Statistical analysis

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the post hoc Sheffé test for multiple comparisons was performed using the software Siphar 4.0 (France). The comparison of two groups (t Student test) was performed with Statgraphics® 5.0 statistical package (Statistical Graphics Corporation, Rockville, MD, USA). Differences between groups were considered to be significant at a level of P less than 0.05.

Table 1
Concentration of the samples for cell cultures studies.

Sample	Concentration (µg/ml)
Mt/ch	Low: 5
	Medium: 50
	High: 500
Ch	Low: 3.3
	Medium: 33.3
	High: 333
Mt	Low: 1.67
	Medium: 16.7
	High: 167

Fig. 2. Culture inserts used for wound-healing measurements.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Water uptake measurements

Fig. 3 shows the water uptake profiles of nanocomposite (Mt/ch) and free components (Ch base and Mt) in 0.1 M HCl. As observed the behavior of the clay mineral was different from that of the pure polymer. Mt immediately levelled off in a plateau, whereas Ch hydrated gradually, due to the progressive formation of the corresponding soluble hydrochloride salt in contact with the medium. After 20 min (1200 s) approximately, the polymer was fully hydrated and the total amount of medium absorbed was 11.5 g/g dry polymer, that is, significantly higher (P<0.001, one-way ANOVA, post hoc Scheffé test) than the amount absorbed by the clay mineral. Nanocomposite achieved final amount absorbed of about 9 g/g. Data were normalized as a function of the actual amount of Ch present in the Mt/ch nanocomposite. The water uptake profile seemed have the same pattern of that of Mt, indicating that the solubility of the polymer in 0.1 M HCl was reduced by the presence of the clay mineral. Since drug release is strictly related with hydration, this result corroborated the hypothesis postulated in a previous work, where drug release from Mt/ch nanocomposite in acidic medium was lower than the observed with Ch alone (Aguzzi et al., 2010).

3.2. Mucoadhesive properties

Mucoadhesion measurements followed the trend Ch > nanocomposite > clay mineral. Ch was characterized by the highest mucoadhesive potential (2.75 ± 0.10).

Fig. 3. Water uptake profiles of the samples in 0.1 M HCl (mean values ± s.e.; n=6).

In fact it is known that Ch possesses mucoadhesive properties, due to the presence of many amino groups in the polymer chains that form hydrogen bonds with glycoproteins in the mucus (Lim et al., 2000) and also ionic interactions between positively charged amino groups and negatively charged sialic acid residues of mucin. Clay mineral was also able to interact with the mucin, although the normalized mucoadhesion parameter (0.71 ± 0.03) was significantly lower compared with Ch ($p < 0.001$, one-way ANOVA post hoc Scheffé test). Nanocomposite showed an intermediate behavior (0.85 ± 0.03). Probably, in the nanocomposite the mobility of the polymer chains was reduced by the interaction of the clay mineral, reducing contact/interpenetration with the substrate. A similar behavior was observed by other authors, studying bioadhesion of nanocomposite between alginate and other kind of layered clay mineral (Pongjanyakul and Sukri, 2009).

3.3. Cell viability

In Fig. 4a, cell viability over each sample after 3 h of incubation is given. At the concentrations studied, Ch and nanocomposite did not

significantly reduce cell viability compared with the blank (culture medium without serum), indicating good biocompatibility properties for these materials. However, in the case of clay mineral at high concentration a significant reduction of cell viability ($p < 0.001$, one-way ANOVA post hoc Scheffé test) was observed. This effect was observed by other authors: they suggested that high amounts of clay particles could block the most of the channels on cell membranes, causing the cell death (Wang et al., 2008). Fig. 4b refers to cell viability obtained after 24 h of incubation with nanocomposite and pure components. For all the samples at all the concentrations considered the viability values were comparable or higher than that of the blank (culture medium without serum). In the case of Ch, viability increased progressively with increasing polymer concentration, compared to the blank. It is known that Ch chains can enhance cell growth both because of their capacity to adhere to the (negatively charged) cell membranes (Wang et al., 2010) and their ability to bind serum factors, such as growth factors (Howling et al., 2001). Clay mineral also increased cell viability at low and intermediate concentrations, reaching values significantly ($p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA post hoc Scheffé test) higher than the obtained with Ch at the same concentration. It could be suggested that a limited amount of clay

Fig. 4. Cell viability after 3 h (a) and 24 h (b) of incubation with the samples studied. Positive control: untreated cells in complete medium; blank: untreated cells in medium without serum; negative control: Triton[®]X100 (Fluka, Italy). See Table 1 for the meaning of the sample concentrations (low, medium, high) (mean values \pm s.e.; $n = 8$).

Fig. 5. Photographs of cell cultures from wound-healing test (bar is 200 μ m).

mineral particles might be engulfed by the cells through endocytosis, resulting in increased mitochondrial activity, rather than in effective cell proliferation activity (Lin et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2008). At higher concentrations, cell viability was reduced in line with the aforementioned observed results (Fig. 4a). The nanocomposite partially reflected the behavior of the free components. Cell viability increased with increasing nanocomposite concentration from low to intermediate level. However, at higher concentrations cell viability did not further increase, showing an intermediate value between Ch and Mt.

3.4. Wound-healing measurements

Wound-healing measurements were done in order to verify the results of cell proliferation obtained by WST-1 test. These measurements allowed a direct observation of cell growth, excluding possible misunderstandings in the interpretation of WST-1 test. Experiments were performed on nanocomposite and free components at the intermediate concentration, where WST-1 test revealed an increase in cell proliferation for all the samples studied, compared with the blank.

Fig. 6. Gap reduction after different incubation times (mean values \pm s.e.; n = 3-5).

In Fig. 5 photographs of cell cultures after different incubation times are given, showing the progression of the gap over each sample as a function of time. Results were expressed as average percentage of gap size after established times compared to time zero, as it is shown in Fig. 6. At time zero, gap's size was in all cases the maximum allowed (assumed 100%). For each sample there was a significant total effect of time in the reduction of wound area in the range 0-72 h ($p < 0.001$, one-way ANOVA). When comparison of two samples was performed (considering subsequent time intervals for each sample), in almost all cases the differences of area at different times were still significant at a 95% level. The results of these comparisons are given in Table 2, where the p values of statistical evaluation performed are reported. As for blank sample, the area reduction was not significant for the comparison between 24 and 48 h indicating a slow proliferation at early time. As for the Mt/ch nanocomposite and Ch, the area reduction was significant at all times, indicating a constant and progressive reduction of wound area, faster than that determined for blank sample. As for Mt sample, the reduction of the wound area was significant only between 48 and 72 h, indicating also in this case a slower proliferation as that of blank and corroborating that the previously observed augment in cell viability (WST-1 test at 24 h) might be due to an increase in mitochondrial activity, induced by the cellular uptake of the clay particles. It is known that in endocytosis processes, mitochondria provide the necessary energy (trapped in ATP) for vesicular transport and for the processing of lysosomal enzymes in the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus (Nelson et al., 2008).

These results indicated that the Caco-2 growth rate was predominantly enhanced by the nanocomposite and Ch. The observed area reduction also suggested an effective stimulation of cell growth by Ch (as previously described in literature (Howling et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2008)) and nanocomposite. According to Lavie and Stotzky (1986) montmorillonite may develop London-van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonding with cells, promoting cell adhesion that, in nanocomposite, should allow Ch to enhance cell growth.

For each time there was not a significant effect of sample in the reduction of wound area (one-way ANOVA). When comparison of two samples was performed the only significant difference that could be evidenced was between blank and nanocomposite at 48 h ($p < 0.05$). At 24 h all samples presented an area of 80% with respect to the initial value, without significant differences between samples (one-way ANOVA). At 48 h the wound area ranged between 40% (Mt/ch) and about 60% for blank with intermediate values for the other samples. After 72 h, in all cases the wound area was reduced to less than 20% of the initial area.

4. Conclusions

According to the results, the prepared Mt/ch nanocomposite possessed mucoadhesive properties combined with lower hydration properties in acidic environment compared with pure Ch.

From cell cultures experiments, Ch and nanocomposite showed good biocompatibility on Caco-2 cells in the concentration range studied (5-500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Nanocomposite and Ch also exhibited a progressive

Table 2
p value obtained for two sample comparison of groups at different times (t Student).

Time (h)	Blank	Mt/ch	Ch	Mt
0-24	0.013	0.003	0.008	0.063
24-48	0.118	<0.001	0.003	0.053
48-72	0.037	0.004	0.019	0.032
0-48	0.004	<0.001	<0.001	0.011
0-72	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.003
24-72	0.007	<0.001	<0.001	0.002

p value considered significant below 0.05.

reduction in wound area, indicating an effective stimulation of Caco-2 proliferation by these samples.

We conclude that a new biohybrid material was produced by interaction between Ch and Mt, showing promising properties for pharmaceutical applications, especially for designing of modified drug delivery systems.

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